

Biological Activity of Some 2-Amino 4,5,6,7-Tetrahydro Benzo(b)-Thiophenes and Their Derivatives

J. D. RAMANATHAN*, D. G. NAMBOOTHIRI †
Medicinal Chemistry Division

G. F. SHAH, A. V. RADHAKRISHNAN
Department of Pharmacology

H. J. MEHTA and A. C. PADHYA
Department of Microbiology

Sarabhai Research Centre, Post Box 162 Baroda-390 001

Manuscript received 7 January 1978, accepted 7 July 1978

Various 2-amino-4, 5, 6, 7-tetrahydro benzo (b)-thiophenes were synthesised by the Gewald reaction. These were converted into the schiffs bases, aryl and hetero aryl derivatives and then were evaluated for their pharmacological, antibacterial, antifungal and antitubercular activities. Some of the compounds synthesised showed promising activity.

MANY of the clinically active local anaesthetics are dialkylaminoalkyl amides and dialkylaminoalkyl esters of a variety of carboxylic acids¹. A related series of dialkylaminoalkyl esters of benzo (b)-thiophene-2-carboxylic acid and also some of the benzo (b)-thiophene carboxamides have been claimed to be useful as hypotensive, antiviral and antifungal agents^{2,3}. Campaign and coworkers have carried out considerable work on the syntheses and pharmacological evaluation of compounds possessing the benzo (b)-thiophene nucleus⁴⁻⁷.

In this communication we wish to report the syntheses and biological activity of the derivatives of 2-amino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro benzo (b)-thiophenes, the general structure of which is given in the Reaction Scheme I. Some of the compounds in this series have been reported by Manhas and coworkers in their preparation of substituted thienopyrimidones^{8,9}. In our studies, a few of the compounds seemed to have promising pharmacological and antimicrobial activities and one of them was comparable to aspirin in its analgesic activity. But none of the compounds showed any significant activity in the central nervous system, and cardiovascular areas. One of them however, has shown pin worm activity.

Results and Discussion

The compounds were screened for analgesic activity by the method of Witkins *et al*¹⁰ and for anti-inflammatory activity by the method of Winter *et al*¹¹, using aspirin and phenylbutazone as standards respectively. Compound 25 showed moderate analgesic activity and no anti-inflammatory activity. The presence of carboxamido group at R₁ (33) retained the activity but did not enhance it. But carbethoxy group as in (3) made the compound considerably active in the anti-inflammatory field. Retaining the carbethoxy group and changing the other substituents did not enhance the activity. An N-(4-carbethoxy phenyl) carboxamido substituent as in (46) gave a compound with slight anti-inflammatory activity. This increased further when an N-methyl carboxamido group was introduced (58). moderate analgesic activity was shown by (61) a cyano substituted compound. Changing the substituent as in (43) produced a compound with analgesic activity

* Present Address : Wockhardt Pvt. Ltd., L-1, Chilkalthana, Jalgaon Road, Aurangabad - 431 003, Maharashtra.

† Author to whom all correspondence should be addressed.

comparable to that of aspirin. This compound also showed good antiinflammatory activity. Search for a more active compound by varying the substitution at R₂ was not fruitful.

The *in vitro* antibacterial, antifungal and antitubercular activities of compounds were studied by the serial dilution technique¹² using dimethyl formamide as solvent.

In the present study fifteen compounds showed antimicrobial activity. Compound (1) with a carbethoxy and 2-hydroxy benzal grouping was active against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *A/R S. Aureus* at 25 mcg/ml level. This also showed antifungal activity against *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Microsporium gypseum* and *Phialophora jeanselmi* at 25,

12.5 to 25 and 25 to 50 mcg/ml levels. This was also the only compound in the series to show activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R₇). Introduction of a bromo substituent as in (2) resulted in the loss of antitubercular activity but retained the others. Presence of nitro group as in (14) resulted in an increased antibacterial activity. The compound showed activity against *S. aureus* and *A/R S. aureus* at 3.125 mcg/ml levels. Change of position of the nitro group as in (15) resulted in the total loss of antibacterial activity. Compounds (6) and (9) showed the same antifungal activity. Compound (8) with a 2-hydroxy-5-(*p*-nitro phenyl azo-) benzal substitution did not show any activity.

Compounds (15),(16 and (36), all 2-carboxamid

TABLE-I

Comp. No.	R ₁	R ₂	M.P °C	Nitrogen Found %	Analysis % Calculated
1.	Carbethoxy-	2-Hydroxybenzal-	124-25	4.55	4.25
2.	Carbethoxy-	2-Hydroxy-5-Bromobenzal-	110-12	3.24	3.43
3.	Carbethoxy-	3-Methoxy-4-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzal-	85-86	3.30	3.55
4.	Carboxamido-	2-Hydroxybenzal-	215-16	9.18	9.34
5.	Carboxamido-	2-Hydroxy-5-bromobenzal-	215-17	7.50	7.39
6.	Carbethoxy-	2-Hydroxy-5-(<i>p</i> -chloro phenylazo)benzal-	191-92	8.87	8.98
7.	Carboxamido-	2-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzal-	> 300	8.34	8.37
8.	Carbethoxy-	2-Hydroxy-5-(<i>p</i> -nitrophenylazo)benzal-	217-18	12.02	11.71
9.	Carbethoxy-	2-Hydroxy-5-(<i>p</i> -sulfo phenylazo)benzal-	> 300	7.80	8.18
10.	<i>N</i> -(<i>p</i> -chloro-phenyl)-carboxamido-	2-Hydroxybenzal-	242-44	6.72	6.82
11.	<i>N</i> -(<i>p</i> -chloro phenyl)-carboxamido-	2-Hydroxy-5-bromobenzal-	254-56	5.50	5.72
12.	<i>N</i> -(<i>p</i> -chloro phenyl)-carboxamido-	2-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzal-	247-49	6.64	6.29
13.	Carbethoxy-	2-Hydroxy-3-nitrobenzal	144-45	7.74	7.48
14.	Carbethoxy-	2-Hydroxy-5-nitrobenzal-	204-05	7.16	7.48
15.	Carboxamido-	2-Hydroxy-3-nitrobenzal-	198-99 (d)	11.92	12.17
16.	Carboxamido-	2-Hydroxy-5-nitrobenzal-	> 300	11.83	12.17
17.	<i>N</i> -Methyl-carboxamido-	2-Hydroxybenzal-	219-21	8.78	8.92
18.	<i>N</i> -Methyl-carboxamido-	2-Hydroxy-5-bromobenzal-	249-50	6.94	7.12
19.	<i>N</i> -Methyl-carboxamido-	2 Hydroxy-3-nitrobenzal-	240-41	11.67	11.70
20.	<i>N</i> -Methyl-carboxamido-	2-Hydroxy-5-nitrobenzal-	252-54	11.33	11.70
21.	<i>N</i> -Methyl-carboxamido-	2-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzal-	240-42	7.80	8.03
22.	Cyano-	2-Hydroxybenzal-	194-95	9.81	9.93
23.	Cyano-	2-Carboxymethyloxy benzal-	185-86	8.10	8.24
24.	Cyano-	4-Methoxybenzal-	110-11	9.08	9.46
25.	Cyano	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzal-	227-29	8.16	8.08
26.	Cyano-	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxybenzal-	144 46	9.20	8.97
27.	Cyano-	3, 4-Methylenedioxybenzal-	168-70	8.72	9.03
28.	Cyano-	Indolyl-	207-09	13.69	13.77
29.	Cyano-	3-Chloro-4-hydroxybenzal-	228-30	8.44	8.84
30.	Cyano-	2, 4-Dichlorobenzal-	180 81	8.72	8.36
31.	Cyano-	3-Hydroxy benzal-	197-99	9.47	9.93
32.	Cyano-	4-Hydroxy benzal-	242-43	9.61	9.93
33.	Carboxamido	3-Methoxy-4-Hydroxy-5-Chlorobenzal	232-33	7.34	7.68
34.	Cyano-	4-Chlorobenzal-	153-54	8.78	9.31
35.	Carboxamido-	3-Hydroxybenzal-	205-07	9.13	9.34
36.	Carboxamido-	3-Chloro-4-hydroxybenzal	212-14	8.20	8.37
37.	Cyano-	4-Nitrobenzal-	185-87	13.99	13.50
38.	Carboxamido-	4-Nitrobenzal-	211-12	11.62	12.76
39.	Carboxamido-	4-Hydroxybenzal-	228-30	9.30	9.34
40.	Carboxamido-	Pyrroly-	215-16 (d)	15.02	15.38
41.	Carboxamido-	Indole-2-one-3-yl.	228-30 (d)	12.30	12.90

Note : All melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE-2

Comp. No.	R ₁	R ₂	M.P. °C	Nitrogen Found	Analysis % Calculated
42.	Carbethoxy-	Dichloroacetyl-	108-10	4.31	4.17
43.	Carboxamido-	H-	176-78	14.16	14.27
44.	Carbethoxy-	7-Chloro-4-quinolyl-	164-66	6.93	7.20
45.	N-(4-chlorophenyl) carboxamido-	H-	145-47	9.41	9.14
46.	Carbethoxy-	Carbethoxy-	93-95	4.10	4.71
47.	N-(4-carbethoxyphenyl) carboxamido-	H-	206-08	8.24	8.18
48.	N-(4-nitrophenyl) carboxamido-	H-	168-70	13.74	13.24
49.	N-(4-sulfamoyl phenyl) carboxamido-	H-	219-21	11.41	11.96
50.	Carbethoxy-	2-Methyl-3, 5-dinitrophenylcarbonyl-	163-64	9.53	9.70
51.	Carboxamido-	carbethoxy-	204-05	10.20	10.45
52.	Carbethoxy-	3, 5-Dinitrophenylcarbonyl-	171-72	10.30	10.02
53.	Carboxamido-	3, 5-Dinitro phenyl carbonyl-	285-86	13.75	14.35
54.	Carboxamido-	2-Methyl-3, 5-dinitrophenylcarbonyl-	252-53	14.03	13.87
55.	N-(2-Methyl-4-chlorophenyl) carboxamido-	H-	157-59	8.73	8.74
56.	N-(2, 6-Dimethylphenyl) carboxamido-	H-	199-200	10.55	9.34
57.	Carbethoxy-	Thiazolidine-2, 4-dione-5-acetyl-	218-20	6.94	7.33
58.	N-methylcarboxamido-	H-	169-72	13.11	13.34
59.	Carboxamido	7-chloro-4-quinolyl-	243-45	11.64	11.74
60.	Cyano-	7-chloro-4-quinolyl-	> 300	11.80	12.37
61.	Cyano-	H-	144-46	15.00	15.73
62.	Cyano-	Acetyl-	215-16	12.33	12.73

* All melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE-3 ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY (*in vitro*) OF SOME 4, 5, 6, 7-TETRAHYDRO-BENZO (b) THIOPHENE DERIVATIVES

Comp. No.	Antibacterial activity		Antifungal activity			Antitubercular activity M. Tuberculosis
	S. aureus	A/RS. aureus	Tr. mentagrophytes	M. gypseum	Ph. Jeanselmi	
1.	25	25	25	12.5 ~ 25	25 ~ 50	50
2.	25	25	25	25	50	-
3.	-	-	25 ~ 50	50	-	-
6.	-	-	50	50	-	-
7.	-	-	50	50	50	-
9.	-	-	50	50	-	-
10.	-	-	50	50	-	-
13.	-	-	12.5	12.5	25	-
14.	3.125	3.125	25	25	25	-
15.	-	-	50	50	-	-
16.	-	-	50	50	-	-
36.	-	-	50	50	-	-
42.	50	50	50	25	-	-
49.	-	-	50	50	-	-
55.	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	-

(-) No activity.

derivatives showed almost identical antifungal activity. But (7) with a 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzal substituent showed activity against *Phialophora Jeanselmi* also at 50 mcg/ml level. Compound (10) exhibited similar activity as (15) and (16). But addition of a bromo or chloro substituent as in (11) or (12) resulted in total loss of activity. Changing the substitution at R₁ as in (49) did not increase the activity, however the presence of an additional methyl group as in (55) increased the antibacterial and antifungal activities considerably. None of the other compounds

showed any significant activity. In parasitic field, compound (48) was active against pin worms of rodents at 400 mg/kg level when given by the per oral route for 3 days.

Experimental

The compounds (43), (45), (47), (58) and (61) were prepared by the Gewald reaction.

TABLE-4 PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF SOME 4, 5, 6, 7-TETRAHYDROBENZO (b)-THIOPHENE DERIVATIVES

Compound No.	Analgesic activity	Antiinflammatory activity
3.	+	+++
8.	+	-
9.	+	-
10.	-	+
11.	+	+
12.	-	++
25.	++	-
33.	++	-
41.	++	+
43.	+++	++
44.	+	-
45.	-	+
58.	-	++
59.	+	+
60.	+	++
61.	++	++
62.	+	++

- No activity
+ Slight activity
++ Moderate activity
+++ Significant activity

2-Amino-3-carboxamido-4, 5, 6, 7-tetrahydro benzo (b)-thiophene(43) : Cyclohexylidene cyano acetamide (15 gms ; 0.1 mole), powdered sulphur (3.2 gms ; 0.1 gram atom) and triethyl amine (1.0 ml) were taken in alcohol (100 ml) and kept in a water bath at 50-60° for 3 hrs. Cooled and kept the mixture overnight. The separated product was filtered, dried and recrystallised from alcohol. Yield, 16 gms, m.p. 176-78° (Found : N, 14.16% Calculated for C₉H₁₂N₂OS...N, 14.27%). Other starting compounds reported in this series were prepared by starting with the corresponding derivatives of cyclohexylidene cyano acetic acid.

2-(3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy-5 chloro benzal)-3-carboxamido 4, 5, 6, 7-tetrahydro benzo (b)-thiophene (33) : Compound (44), (3.92 gms ; 0.02 mole) in alcohol (40 ml) was added to 5-chloro vanillin (3.72 gms ; 0.02 mole) in alcohol (40 ml) containing glacial acetic

acid (3 ml). The product separated out on warming. Cooled, filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. Yield, 5 gms. m.p. 232-33°. (Found ; N, 7.34%. Calculated for C₁₇H₁₇ClN₂O₃S. N, 7.68%). The other compounds reported in Table 1 were prepared in the same manner.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. V. Srinivasan, Director for his keen interest in the work and kind permission to publish this paper. We also express our thanks to members of the Parasitology and the analytical departments for their help.

References

1. A. BURGER in "Medicinal Chemistry", (Ed) A. BURGER, Interscience Publishers Inc. New York, 1960, p. 441.
2. W. VOEGTLI, U.S.P., 1958, 2857, 383, *Chem. Abs.*, 1959, 53, 6249.
3. R. W. GOETTSCHE and G.A. WESE, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1958, 47, 319.
4. E. CAMPAIGNE, T. BOSIN and E. S. NEISS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1967, 10, 270.
5. E. CAMPAIGNE and W. E. KREIGHBAUM, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 1327.
6. E. CAMPAIGNE and L. BOSIN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1967, 10, 947.
7. E. CAMPAIGNE, E. D. WEINBERG, G. CARLSON and E. S. NEISS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 136.
8. M. S. MANHAS, S. D. SHARMA and S. G. AMIN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 106.
9. M. S. MANHAS, S. G. AMIN, and B. DAYAL, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1976, 13, 633.
10. C. B. WITCIN, C. F. HUEBNER, F. GALDI, E. O. KEEFE, P. SPITALETTA and A. J. PLUMMER, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1961, 133, 400.
11. C. A. WINTER, E. A. RISLEY and G. W. NUSS, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1962, 111, 544.
12. Mackie and McCartney's "Handbook of Bacteriology" (Ed) R. CRUICKSHANK, E.S. LIVINGSTON Ltd., Edinburgh, Scotland, 1962, 407.
13. K. GEWALD, E. SCHINKE and H. BOETTCHER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1966, 99, 94.